

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND IT'S IMPACT ON ADJUSTMENT AMONG TRIBAL STUDENTS OF HIGH SCHOOL IN DADRA AND NAGAR HAVELI

Dr. Sarika M. Patel

SSR College of Education Sayli, Silvassa. U.T of DNH. Pin : 396230 India.

1.1 Introduction

In 21st century, beyond the traditional area of general intelligence, intrapersonal and interpersonal skills like emotional intelligence, adjustment, creativity, ability of reasoning, problem – solving etc. are at the center of concern. According to Goleman (1995), IQ alone is no more the only measure for success; emotional intelligence and social intelligence also play a big role in person's life. Human beings experience the most difficult changes during their adolescence.

According to Dr. G. Aruna Mohan (2009), adjusted children satisfies majority of his psychological needs on reality level. Education psychology denotes the contribution of emotional intelligence and adjustment to students' performance, health and high spirit. Emotions, being the most significant component of personality, play an important role in one's life.

Researches in different areas of educational psychology denote the contribution of emotional intelligence and adjustment to students' performance, health and high spirit. The result of different researches indicated that emotions, being the most significant component of personality, play an extremely important role in one's life, emotions facilitate person's attitude and behavior towards achieving their goals. Especially an adolescence period of an individual is stormy period in terms of personality, adjustment, somatic variation, intensity of emotions etc. Thus an attempt will be made to check the emotional intelligence and to examine the relationship between emotional intelligence and adjustment among the tribal students of high school.

1.2 Statement of the problem

The study undertaken by the researcher has been entitled as,
“EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND IT'S IMPACT ON ADJUSTMENT AMONG TRIBAL STUDENTS OF HIGH SCHOOL IN DADRA AND NAGAR HAVELI”

1.3 Conceptual and operational definitions of the main words

Definitionsof the terms used in title of the research are as follows:

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE

According to Mayer and Salovey (1999) “Emotional intelligence is the ability to perceive emotions, to access and generate emotions so as to assist thought, to understand emotions and emotional knowledge and to reflectively regulate emotions so as to promote emotional and intellectual growth.”

In the present research emotional intelligence means the emotional intelligence of tribal students of high school in Dadra and Nagar Haveli measured by Mangal Emotional Intelligence Inventory.

ADJUSTMENT

Shaffer (1961) describes adjustment as,

“Adjustment is the process by which a living organism maintains a balance between its needs and the circumstances that influence the satisfaction of these needs.”

In the present research the meaning of adjustment is the adjustment by the tribal students of high school in Dadra and Nagar Haveli measured by Bell’s Adjustment Inventory.

1.4 Objectives of the research

- 1) To study the emotional intelligence of high school students.
- 2) To study the impact of emotional intelligence on four areas of adjustment like home, health, social and emotional in high school students.
- 3) To study the impact of emotional intelligence on adjustment with respect to sex, area and type of institution of high school students.

1.5 Hypothesis of the research

- 1) There is no significant difference between the mean scores of emotional intelligence of boy and girl students.
- 2) There is no significant difference between the mean scores of emotional intelligence of rural and urban high school students.
- 3) There is no significant difference between the mean scores of emotional intelligence of Government and Private high school students.
- 4) There is no significant difference between the mean scores of home adjustment of students having high and low level of emotional intelligence.
- 5) There is no significant difference between the mean scores of health adjustment of students having high and low level of emotional intelligence.
- 6) There is no significant difference between the mean scores of social adjustment of students having high and low level of emotional intelligence.
- 7) There is no significant difference between the mean scores of emotional adjustment of students having high and low level of emotional intelligence.
- 8) There is no significant difference between the mean scores of boy students having high and low level of emotional intelligence.
- 9) There is no significant difference between the mean scores of girl students having high and low level of emotional intelligence.
- 10) There is no significant difference between the mean adjustment scores of boy and girl students having high level of emotional intelligence.
- 11) There is no significant difference between the mean adjustment scores of boy and girl students having low level of emotional intelligence.
- 12) There is no significant difference between the mean adjustment scores of students in rural high schools having high and low level of emotional intelligence.
- 13) There is no significant difference between the mean adjustment scores of students in urban high schools having high and low level of emotional intelligence.
- 14) There is no significant difference between the mean adjustment scores of students in rural and urban high schools having high level of emotional intelligence.

15) There is no significant difference between the mean adjustment scores of students in rural and urban high schools having low level of emotional intelligence.

16) There is no significant difference between the mean adjustment scores of students in government high schools having high and low level of emotional intelligence.

17) There is no significant difference between the mean adjustment scores of students in private high schools having high and low level of emotional intelligence.

18) There is no significant difference between the mean adjustment scores of students in government and private high schools having high level of emotional intelligence.

19) There is no significant difference between the mean adjustment scores of students in government and private high schools having low level of emotional intelligence.

1.6 Importance of the research

1. The result of the present research would be helpful for tribal students. Parents and teachers.
2. The result of the research would be helpful for educationist and policy makers. It would provide guidelines to frame effective curriculum.
3. The result of the present research would provide guidelines to the Department of Rural Development.

1.7 Delimitation of the research

Delimitation of the present research is as follows

1. The present research was limited to the tribal students of high school in Union Territory of Dadra and Nagar Haveli.
2. The present research was limited to tribal students of Std. IX and Std. X present on the day of the scale administration, making the sample of 1638.
3. The emotional intelligence scale (EIS) includes three levels of emotional intelligence. Out of which only two levels i.e. high and low levels emotional intelligence were considered for the present research.
4. The interpretation are held to be valid and reliable to the extent of the reliability and validity of the tools employed in measuring the emotional intelligence and adjustment scores of the students, contained in the research.

1.8 Population and sampling

Population of the present research includes all the high schools of U.T. of Dadra and Nagar Haveli. There were total 39 high schools in U.T. of Dadra and Nagar Haveli. Out of 39 high schools, 27 were situated in rural area whereas 12 high schools were situated in urban area. Fifty percent of high schools were selected from each stratum by using random sampling. There were total 5365 Scheduled Tribe Students in the selected high schools. Out of 5365, thirty percent of the students were selected from the each stratum by applying lottery method. Hence, total 1638 students were selected for the present research.

Table: 1

Sex	Rural Area		Urban Area		Total
	Government School	Private School	Government School	Private School	
Boys	659	70	114	30	873
Girls	596	38	107	24	765
Total	1255	108	221	54	1638

1.9 Variables of the research

Details about variables in the present research is given below.

Table:2

Sr. No.	Variable	Type	Level	Detail
1	Emotional intelligence	Independent	2	High
				Low
2	Adjustment	Dependent(of adjustment pattern and emotional intelligence)	2	High
				Low
3	Sex	Independent	2	Boys
				Girls
4	Area	Independent	2	Rural
				Urban
5	Type of Institution	Independent	2	Goveronment
				Private

1.10 Research tools

1. Emotional Intelligence Scale (EIS) by Arun Kumar Singh and ShrutiNarain(1971).
2. Bell's Adjustment Inventory by R. K. Ojha.

1.11 Research Method

The present research was conducted through descriptive survey method of research.

1.12 Research Design

The aim of the present research was to study emotional intelligence and its impact on adjustment among tribal students of high school. Hence, 1638 tribal students of high school were taken as a sample of the research. Groups of sample were formed on the basis of sex, area of the school and type of the institution. The students selected for the research were administered two tools viz.

Emotional Intelligence Scale and Adjustment Inventory in order to obtain raw scores. After data collection the data was compiled and analyzed with the help of tables and statistical methods.

1.13 Data collection

With prior permission of principals from various schools, the researcher administered two psychological tests viz. Emotional Intelligence scale and Bell's Adjustment Inventory to the tribal students from thirteen government and seven private high schools. After securing student's consent and assurance of co-operation, they were told how to give the tests. Instructions were given to students according to test manuals. Scoring of both the tests was done as per the scoring keys of both the tests.

1.14 Techniques of data analysis

To do the data analysis following techniques were used by the researcher.

1. Mean
2. Standard Deviation
3. t- Test

1.15 Findings of the research

As per the statistical analysis and interpretation of collected data the researcher concluded the following findings.

1. It was found that there was no difference in the emotional intelligence of boy students and girl students.
2. It was found that students from rural schools were having more emotional intelligence than the students from urban school.
3. It was found that students from Private schools were having more emotional intelligence than the students from Government schools.
4. It was concluded that students having high emotional intelligence were having more adjustment at home than the students having low emotional intelligence.
5. It was concluded that students having high emotional intelligence were having more health adjustment than the students having low emotional intelligence.
6. It was concluded that students having high emotional intelligence were having more social adjustment than the students having low emotional intelligence.
7. It was concluded that students having high emotional intelligence were having more health adjustment than the students having low emotional intelligence.
8. It was concluded that boy students having high emotional intelligence were having more adjustment than the boy students having low emotional intelligence.
9. It was concluded that girl students having high emotional intelligence were having more adjustment than the girl students having low emotional intelligence.
10. It was concluded that boy students having high emotional intelligence were having more adjustment than the girl students having low emotional intelligence.
11. It was concluded that boy students having low emotional intelligence were having more adjustment than the girl students having low emotional intelligence.

12. It was concluded that students having high emotional intelligence were having more adjustment than the students having low emotional intelligence from rural high school.
13. It was concluded that students having high emotional intelligence were having more adjustment than the students having low emotional intelligence from urban high school.
14. It was concluded that students having high emotional intelligence from rural high school were having more adjustment than the students from urban high schools.
15. It was concluded that students having low emotional intelligence from urban high school were having more adjustment than the students from rural high schools.
16. It was concluded that students having high emotional intelligence were having more adjustment than the students having low emotional intelligence from Government high schools.
17. It was concluded that students having high emotional intelligence were having more adjustment than the students having low emotional intelligence from Private high schools.
18. It was concluded that students having high emotional intelligence from Private schools were having more adjustment than the students from Government high schools.
19. It was concluded that students having low emotional intelligence from Private schools were having more adjustment than the students from Government high schools.

1.16 Conclusion

In the present scenario of education, development of children is required in order to meet many challenges of their lives. Emotional intelligence is positively higher related with general health, healthy coping style, empathy, happiness etc. Emotional maturity, sensitivity, empathy and ability to manage emotions effectively are important indicators for mental health. A new concept, emotional intelligence with its significance even more than one's general intelligence has emerged on the educational scene.

A child with emotional intelligence and adjustment feels good about herself/himself, enjoys relationships, learn confidently and overcomes her/his difficulties. Emotional intelligence and adjustment contribute a major role to maintain mental health of children. Emotional intelligence is a positive and dynamic topic with enormous implications at all the levels of education. Hence, the researcher aimed to study the emotional intelligence and its impact on adjustment in the present research.

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